

The Invisible Hand of AI Libraries

Shaping Open Source Projects and Communities

Online Appendix

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I. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

One distinguishing feature of OSS is that its source code is openly accessible for anyone to use, modify, and distribute. In contrast to proprietary software developed and owned by individual companies, OSS fosters collaborative and community-driven development Fortunato et al. [1]. These characteristics make OSS a suitable candidate for diverse research in software engineering Gyimothy et al. [2].

A. OSS in Empirical Software Engineering

Mockus et al. [3] compare commercial and open-source methodologies using Mozilla and Apache as examples. They find that while commercial projects rely on explicit coordination, OSS projects like Apache use decentralized communication. Mozilla faces challenges due to module interdependencies, while Apache’s approach emphasizes modularity. Leveraging the open-source community for low-interdependence tasks can improve productivity.

Similarly, Gyimothy et al. [2] conducted a study to assess the quality and reliability of OSS systems, mainly focusing on Mozilla, a widely used web and email suite. They calculated

object-oriented metrics proposed by Chidamber et al. [4] to analyze fault-proneness in Mozilla’s source code. Moreover, Yu et al. [5] conducted a large-scale empirical study on Java annotations, analyzing 1,094 OSS projects on GitHub. They investigated annotation usage, evolution, and impact, revealing 10 novel findings. Similarly, we are also interested in the context of OSS projects. Nonetheless, the author focused on Java annotations, while our study focuses on AI libraries and technologies.

Arberdour et al. [6] highlights the significance of the OSS community’s research on OSS quality, emphasizing the shift towards empirical data over subjective opinions. Moreover, they discuss the consensus in the literature on the key components of OSS quality. The authors review the state of the art, extracting lessons and exploring the divergences and potential inclusion of OSS quality approaches into closed-source software development methods.

Esposito et al. [7] investigated the hidden bugs, i.e., buggy untouched methods, that remained dormant for various releases of OSS projects. Similarly, Esposito et al. [8] performed a large-scale analysis on OSS vulnerability severity according to SonarQube and the National Vulnerability (NVD) Datasets to assess whether the NVD vulnerability severity was correlated with SQ severity levels. Finally, Esposito et al. [9] performed a large-scale OSS-oriented test of static analysis security testing tools. Moreover, recent studies employed the ready availability of OSS development history to improve JIT defect prediction

B. AI libraries in Software Engineering

AI stimulated new research approaches to each software engineering task [10]. Wan et al. [11], investigated how incorporating machine learning into systems impacts software development practices. They conducted both qualitative interviews and a quantitative survey to identify differences between developing machine learning systems and traditional systems. The study revealed significant disparities in software engineering aspects such as requirements, design, testing, and process, as well as in work characteristics like skill variety, problem-solving, and task identity.

Moran et al. [12] devised an automated approach called ReDraw to streamline the transformation of GUI mock-ups

into code for user-facing software. ReDraw utilizes computer vision techniques and deep convolutional neural networks. A data-driven algorithm then generates a hierarchical GUI structure, enabling automatic assembly of prototype applications for the Android platform. Esposito et al. [13], compiled a systematic dataset review on the usage of AI in the field of vulnerability prediction.

Furthermore, Liu et al. [14] conducted an empirical study on Stack Overflow to explore developers’ challenges in finding suitable ML/DL libraries for AI tasks. Based on their findings, they proposed MLTaskKG, a task-oriented ML/DL library recommendation approach. MLTaskKG utilizes a knowledge graph to capture AI tasks, ML/DL models, implementations, repositories, and their relationships. By extracting knowledge from various sources, including ML/DL resource websites, papers, and frameworks, MLTaskKG recommends libraries matching developers’ requirements.

Xu et al. [15], address the challenge of turning conceptual ideas into code, especially when dealing with unfamiliar library APIs, by investigating the promise and challenges of using ML for code generation and retrieval within the PyCharm IDE. They developed a plugin for PyCharm that combines code generation and retrieval functionality and orchestrates virtual environments to collect user events. While qualitative surveys indicate positive developer experiences, quantitative results regarding increased productivity, code quality, and program correctness are inconclusive. The study identifies critical points for improving future machine learning-based code assistants and demonstrates developers’ preferences between code generation and retrieval.

Finally, Wang et al. [16] conducted a 12-year Systematic Literature Review on 1,428 ML/DL-related SE papers published between 2009 and 2020. Their analysis highlighted the impacts, complexities, and challenges of applying ML/DL techniques to SE tasks. They categorized the rationales for ML/DL technique selection into five themes and examined issues related to reproducibility, replicability, and model choices in SE tasks.

C. AI libraries in OSS

Dilhara et al. [17] presented a large-scale empirical study to examine the challenges developers face utilizing ML libraries in Software-2.0 development. Key findings include a significant increase in the adoption of ML libraries, various usage patterns, and unique challenges such as the binary incompatibility of trained ML models. Our study focuses on the broader AI spectrum of libraries, evaluating the impact of adopting them.

Tufano et al. [18] investigated how developers use Large Language Models, like OpenAI’s ChatGPT, in OSS projects. Out of the 1,501 instances of potential ChatGPT usage in open-source projects, the authors narrowed them down to 467 actual ChatGPT instances. [18] categorized these instances into 45 tasks developers automate using ChatGPT, hence helping developers understand how to use LLMs effectively and providing researchers with insight into tasks that can

benefit and those that do not from automated solutions. Our study focuses on the usage of AI libraries, thus including LLMs, in OSS projects, intending to investigate the impact that the adoption of such libraries has on community engagement and the technical ecosystem.

II. EMPIRICAL STUDY DESIGN

RQ₁ (Adoption). How widespread is the adoption of AI-related libraries in open-source software projects?

RQ_{1.1} Does AI adoption differ between Java and Python projects?

This *RQ* aims to measure the extent of AI library adoption in OSS projects. AI adoption captures **whether and how much** a project integrates AI features and capabilities through external components, i.e., libraries. According to [19]–[21], we can analyze evidence of a project dependency on three levels:

- **Dependency-level evidence:** importing or referencing AI/ML libraries (e.g., TensorFlow, PyTorch, Scikit-learn, Hugging Face Transformers).
- **Code-level evidence:** using classes, functions, or APIs belonging to these libraries.
- **Commit-level or release-level evidence:** identifying when AI libraries were introduced and whether they continue to be maintained or expanded.

In this first *RQ*, we aim to measure the dependency-level evidence, specifically whether the OSS project includes references to AI libraries in its list of dependencies. Furthermore, we are keen to focus on Java and Python because they represent two dominant yet contrasting ecosystems in software development [22]. Python is the de facto language for AI and machine learning, offering a rich ecosystem of libraries, including TensorFlow, PyTorch, and scikit-learn [23], [24]. In contrast, Java is widely adopted in enterprise and large-scale software systems, where AI integration is emerging [25]. Studying both allows us to capture differences between experimentation-oriented (Python) and production-oriented (Java) environments. Other languages were excluded as they either lack mature AI ecosystems (e.g. Go) [26], [27], or they are more challenging, e.g., steeper learning curve, memory management complexity, that may affect adoption compared to higher-level languages (e.g. C++) [28], or are less representative of large, diverse open-source communities suitable for comparative analysis [23].

III. CONTROLLING FOR CONFOUNDING FACTORS IN RQ2 AND RQ3

Observational studies on open-source software are inherently exposed to confounding factors, as project characteristics may simultaneously influence both technology adoption and the metrics of interest. On the one hand, **this study aim to identify potential non-trivial confounding factors** to use in a upcoming cohort study. On the other hand, in the

TABLE I
REPOSITORY INCLUSION CRITERIA

Criterion	Condition
Archived or Fork	Repository is neither archived nor a fork
Last Activity	The last activity on the repository is less than six months old
Contributors	Repository has at least three contributors
Star Count	Repository has 50 or more stars
SBOM Availability	The GitHub repository allows access to the SBOM

context of RQ2 and RQ3, project size, popularity, activity, and application domain are particularly relevant, as they may correlate with both AI library adoption and repository- or code-level metrics.

To mitigate these risks, our study adopts a multi-level strategy that combines **sampling controls**, **analysis-time adjustments**, and **robustness checks**.

A. Sampling-Level Controls

At the data collection stage, we apply strict inclusion criteria to reduce variance stemming from unstable or atypical repositories. Specifically, we exclude forks and archived projects, require recent activity within six months prior to data collection, enforce a minimum of three contributors, and include only repositories with at least 50 GitHub stars. The star threshold is used as a proxy for project popularity, following prior empirical work (Table I). These criteria help reduce confounding effects related to project immaturity, inactivity, and extremely low visibility, which are known to affect both adoption behavior and software metrics.

B. Analysis-Time Controls

To further account for confounding in RQ2 and RQ3, we explicitly control for project characteristics during analysis. Rather than relying solely on aggregate comparisons between AI-adopting and non-adopting projects, we perform **stratified analyses** based on key confounding variables. In particular, projects are grouped into homogeneous strata according to size-related indicators (e.g., code volume) and popularity (e.g., star-count quantiles). Comparisons are then conducted within each stratum, reducing the likelihood that observed differences are driven by systematic differences in project scale or visibility.

In addition, when feasible, we apply **matching-based comparisons**, pairing AI-adopting projects with non-adopting projects that exhibit similar values for size, popularity, and project age.

C. Domain-Related Considerations

Project domain represents a more challenging confounding factor to operationalize at scale. To address this, we leverage coarse-grained domain indicators derived from repository metadata, such as GitHub topics and tags, when available and READMEs. These indicators are used to support stratification

or matching, enabling comparisons among projects operating in similar application contexts. Nonetheless, we acknowledge that domain effects cannot be entirely eliminated and explicitly treat residual domain-related confounding as a threat to internal validity.

D. Robustness and Interpretation

Finally, to ensure the stability of findings, we assess whether conclusions for RQ2 and RQ3 remain consistent across different strata and matched samples, and we report effect sizes alongside statistical significance. This approach supports a more cautious and transparent interpretation of results, emphasizing practical relevance rather than relying solely on p-values.

IV. SOFTWARE METRICS

Software metrics provide quantitative insights into various aspects of software design, implementation, and maintainability [7]. They help developers and project managers assess code quality, identify potential issues, and improve software reliability and performance [7].

Regarding such metrics, Table II presents those that can be collected using the "full metric" parameter in the SciTool's Understand static analysis tool. These metrics, including cyclomatic complexity, line counts, and class coupling, measure different dimensions of code, such as its complexity, readability, cohesion, and interdependencies, offering a comprehensive view of software quality.

V. REPOSITORY METRICS

Repository metrics provide valuable insights into the activity, health, and community engagement of a software project hosted on platforms like GitHub. These metrics help developers, maintainers, and stakeholders understand the level of collaboration, issue resolution, and code evolution in the repository. The table below lists key repository metrics, their descriptions, and their classifications according to [29]–[32].

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TABLE II
SOFTWARE METRICS FROM SCITTOOLS' UNDERSTAND.

ACRONYM: L - LANGUAGE; J - JAVA, P - PYTHON, B - BOTH; G - GRANULARITY: C - CLASS, F - FUNCTION, M - METHOD, PR - PROJECT

Name	Description	L	G
AvgCountLineBlank	Average number of blank lines per method or function.	B	M
AvgCountLineCode	Average number of lines of code per method or function.	B	M
AvgCyclomatic	Average cyclomatic complexity of methods/functions within a class or file.	B	C/F
AvgCountLineComment	Average number of comment lines per method or function.	B	M
CountClassBase	Number of immediate base classes a class inherits from.	B	C
CountClassCoupled	Number of unique classes that a class is directly coupled to.	B	C
CountClassDerived	Number of classes that directly inherit from a given class.	B	C
CountDeclClass	Number of class declarations within a file or namespace.	B	F
CountDeclFunction	Number of function declarations within a file or namespace.	P	F
CountDeclInstanceMethod	Number of instance method declarations within a class.	B	C
CountDeclInstanceVariablePrivate	Number of private instance variable declarations within a class.	B	C
CountDeclMethod	Number of method declarations within a class.	B	C
CountLineBlank	Number of blank lines in the code (readability metric).	B	F
CountLineCode	Number of lines containing executable code.	B	F
CountLineComment	Number of lines containing comments in the code.	B	F
CountStmt	Total number of statements in the code.	B	F
Cyclomatic	Cyclomatic complexity of a single method or function.	B	M
MaxCyclomatic	Maximum cyclomatic complexity among all methods/functions.	B	C/F
MaxInheritanceTree	Maximum depth of the inheritance tree for a class.	B	C
MaxNesting	Maximum nesting level of control structures.	B	M
PercentLackOfCohesion	Lack of cohesion in a class (higher = lower cohesion).	B	C
SumCyclomatic	Sum of cyclomatic complexities of all methods/functions.	B	C/F

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TABLE III
REPOSITORY METRICS CLASSIFICATION.
ACRONYMS: **AM** - ACTIVITY; **CEM** - COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT; **ITM** - ISSUE TRACKING; **PRM** - PULL REQUEST; **RMM** - RELEASE MANAGEMENT; **WM** - WORKFLOW; **TM** - TECHNOLOGY METRICS.

Metric Name	Description	Group
Branches	Number of branches in the repository.	AM
Closed Issues	Number of issues that have been resolved or closed.	ITM
Closed Pulls	Number of pull requests that have been merged or closed.	PRM
Comments	Total number of comments on issues and pull requests.	ITM
Commits	Total number of commits made in the repository.	AM
Contributors	Number of unique contributors who have contributed to the repository.	CEM
Dependencies	Number of external dependencies listed in the repository.	RMM
Forks	Number of times the repository has been forked.	CEM
Issues	Total number of issues in the repository (open and closed).	ITM
Languages	Programming languages used in the repository, measured by lines of code.	TM
Open Issues	Number of currently open issues in the repository.	ITM
Open Pulls	Number of currently open pull requests.	PRM
Pulls	Total number of pull requests (open and closed).	PRM
Releases	Total number of releases published in the repository.	RMM
Star Count	Number of stars the repository has received.	CEM
Subscribers	Number of people subscribed to repository notifications.	CEM
Tags	Total number of tags created in the repository.	AM
Topics	Topics or keywords associated with the repository.	TM
Watchers	Number of users watching the repository.	CEM
Workflows	Number of workflows configured for CI/CD in the repository.	WM

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